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Abstract book

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Brachytherapy is better to deliver focal radiotherapy boost in localized prostate cancer

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Radical radiotherapy (RT) is a cornerstone in prostate cancer management, often combined with androgen deprivation therapy (ADT). Delivering higher radiation doses (dose escalation, DE) to the prostate has been shown to improve outcomes by reducing biochemical relapse and disease progression across all risk groups, and by improving survival in high-risk patients. Dose escalation can be achieved using modern external beam radiotherapy (EBRT) techniques or by adding brachytherapy (BT) to EBRT.

Whole-gland DE represents the standard approach in prostate cancer radiotherapy. Brachytherapy has emerged as a superior DE option over EBRT, as demonstrated by numerous retrospective studies, systematic reviews, and three prospective randomized controlled trials. However, concerns have been raised regarding increased toxicity, which could negatively impact patients' quality of life (QoL). To address this, focal boost strategies have been proposed, which deliver higher doses to specific intra-prostatic regions of tumor burden, aiming to improve treatment outcomes without increasing toxicity.

Focal boost can be delivered either with EBRT alone or with a combination of EBRT and BT. Imaging modalities such as multi-parametric magnetic resonance imaging (mpMRI), positron emission tomography (PET-CT) and transrectal ultrasound (TRUS) can be used for the identification and delineation of intra-prostatic lesions. Clinical evidence supports use of brachytherapy in focal boosting, both in high dose rate (HDR) and low dose rate settings, with excellent results. To date, only one study has compared focal boosting with EBRT alone versus EBRT plus BT, finding comparable outcomes but higher tumor doses achieved when brachytherapy was included.

We believe that the use of brachytherapy for focal prostate boost outperforms modern EBRT techniques due to its ability to deliver higher, highly conformal radiation doses directly to the prostate while minimizing exposure of surrounding healthy tissues. Ongoing studies will provide additional long-term follow-up to further support this approach.

Keywords: Prostate cancer, Brachytherapy, Radiotherapy, Androgen deprivation therapy, boost

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